

Problem

Competitive market landscape

Matrix performance	HP-TP	STRATASYS, USA (1998) ESSENTIM, USA TRACTUS3D, NL 3DEVO, NL 3NTR, IT ROBOZE, IT APIUM, DE REPRAP, DE MINIFACTORY, FI INNOVATICA3D, PL INTAMSYS, CN DYNAMICAL3D, ES 3R3DTM, ES etc.	ROBOZE, IT APIUM, DE REPRAP, DE MINIFACTORY, FI INNOVATICA3D, PL INTAMSYS, CN DYNAMICAL3D, ES 3R3DTM, ES etc.	AREVO LABS, USA (2016) DESKTOP METAL, USA (2019) 9T LABS, CH (2019) APS Techsolutions, AT (2021) MARKFORGED, USA (2014/21) ANISOPRINT, RU/LU (2017/21)
	TP			
	Reinforcement performance	Non Reinforced	Short Fiber Reinforced	Continuous Fiber Reinforced

Innovative solution: from AFP to 3DP

Advantages:

- 3DP feedstock lower price
- 3DP feedstock higher quality
- 3DP feedstock open-source
- 3DP feedstock larger variety
- High Performance: mechanical
- High Performance: thermal

HP tapes feedstock: 200-300 EUR/kg

e.g. Competitor_1 feedstock : 2300 EUR/kg
Competitor_2 feedstock : 3000 EUR/kg

RDI Current Status

Technology Readiness Level: TRL 3-

- concept formulation
- virtual prototyping
- PoC physical prototyping
- EPO & PCT patent application

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 712949 (TECNIOspring PLUS) and from the Agency for Business Competitiveness of the Government of Catalonia. Project implemented at the Analysis and Advanced Materials for Structural Design AMADE research group of University of Girona, Spain.

